

Our War Or Not: A Critical Discourse Analysis Of President General Pervez Musharaf's Speech At The UN General Assembly

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 20, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Critical Discourse Analysis; United Nations; Ideology; War On Terror; Global Peace.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5116575</p>	<p><i>Critical discourse analysis (CDA) is previously not a homogenous model, nor a school or a paradigm, but at most a shared perspective in doing linguistics, semantics, or discourse analysis. The objective of CDA is to perceive language use as social practice. The researchers in this paper have done this at the 58th session of the UN General assembly, New York. The theoretical framework used for the analysis is Fairclough's model, 1992. This research paper has analysed the data qualitatively. This research work has explained and clarified the intellectual and invulnerable strategies, ideologies of President Musharraf, Pakistani president for global, political, economic, social and cultural development not only for his own country but for the entire world, especially developing countries. CDA of G-P-M speech shows that his motto is peace, security and development of human rights, implementation of international law, social justice for everyone and multilateral diplomacy by the support of the war on terror and cooperation with the international community. Pervaiz Musharaf has presented a positive and soft image of Pakistan.</i></p>

Introduction

Our critical analysis and explanations of the political and ideological factors in President General Pervez Musharaf speech attempts us to look from a broad vision not only on personal level but on general level and appreciation from those who serve for humanity without any discrimination of caste and creed. And if we see the very first sentence of the speech, "It is with great pleasure that I extend to you our warmest felicitations on your election". Here we analyze in our own perspective and according to our critical analysis and interpretation it is multidimensional but this is very clear that the opening sentences of the President General Pervez Musharaf speech guide us and appreciate the president of UN General Assembly not only for his own personality but for his political achievements. Not only President General Pervez Musharaf appreciates United Nations Secretary-General Kofi Annan and his predecessor H.E Mr. Jan Kavan's efforts for global peace and security, but also appreciate and pay tribute to the memory of Mr. Sergio de Mello and other UN officials who sacrificed their lives in the service of peace. In paragraph 2, "We support Secretary- General Kofi Annan's efforts to infuse a sense of mission in the United Nations and.....", If we analyze and interpret it on political and ideological level, we are clear to understand that President General Pervez Musharaf support Secretary-General efforts because he is the well-wisher of Pakistan as well as Humanity of this mortal world which is full of problems at social, cultural, economic, political and developmental level.

Starting style of President General Pervez Musharaf speech in UN General Assembly on 24th September 2003 is based on applying and attempting a more citizen-centred attitude. And President Pervez Musharaf has unique and unanimous strategy and policy for the development of Pakistan and UN Agenda is also seen in his opening line of the speech.

Framework

This study has used Fairclough (1992) model for critical discourse analysis of the speech of G-P-M. according to Fairclough (1992) model there are three stages for the analysis of the discourse. Personal experience and knowledge, social relations and realization of the identity and reality. Fairclough (1992) is of the view that people belonging to a specific social setup have different relational and expressive norms which is revealed in their speeches.

Age of Cooperation

In paragraph 3, President General Pervez Musharaf clear it that it is the age of cooperation and peace free of ideological confrontations (Bird 2011). But these dreams are dashed by ethnic cleansing in Bosnia, Israeli occupation in Palestine, brutal suppression of Kashmiris demand for self-determination, unending war in Afghanistan and unequal economic globalization. By raising these hot issues President General Pervez Musharaf want to attract the attention of United Nations to solve it peacefully and intellectually.

Support of the War on Terror

In paragraph 4 sentence 1 of the speech, “The terrible terrorist atrocity of 9/11 jolted the foundations of international system” Ayeomoni(2012) , President General Pervez Musharraf make it clear that the terrorist attack has shocked us. Again in paragraph 5 of the speech, “The tragedy of 9/11 transformed security policies and changed geo political calculations. Pakistan took a strategic decision, based on the principles of humanity and our national interest to support the war on terrorism” Van Dajik 2011, the empirical data and the published accounts analyzing General Musharraf’s decision to board the US-led international campaign against terrorism that centred on Afghanistan and Al Qaeda follow diametrically opposite viewpoints. On the one end of the spectrum are government exponents that label this decision as a rational, realistic and pragmatic response in view of the changed global scenario. On the other end is opinion that terms this decision as essentially personal and opportunistic contrary to the national interests of the country.

The key point that is stressed in the following analyses is that there is no black and white explanation and the reality lies somewhere in between these two often conflicting and opposite lines of thinking. The Musharraf government’s decision was the product of multiple stresses and strains that Islamabad faced in the aftermath of the 9/11 World Trade Center (WTC) incident. These ranged from the threatening posture of the United States to the possibility of India assuming a lead role in Afghanistan and changing the geo-politics of the region. This line of reasoning fused well with General Musharraf’s pre -9/11 reformist agenda based on the realization that Pakistan had been a victim, target, recruiting zone, safe-haven and transit-zone for the terrorists’ groupings within and beyond the national frontiers.

Due to blurring and meshing external and internal security dynamics. As a result, the need to have an integrated, sustainable and comprehensive national security policy became more critical. It was essentially a tactical decision based on rational calculation of the country’s strategic priorities. Here the question that may well be asked is with regard to the factors that conditioned General Musharraf’s response as events unfolded and the situation in the immediate aftermath of 9/11 developed.

To begin with, US deputy secretary of state, Richard Armitage told Pakistan’s ISI head General Mehmood: “You are either 100 % with us or 100 % against us. There is no grey area”. Maleeha Lodhi who was at that time serving as Pakistan’s Ambassador to the United States conveyed Washington’s message to Islamabad and got an affirmative answer from General Musharraf asking officials to let Washington know that it would get what it wanted. Terming the decision to be a key US ally as dispassionate. The President General Pervez Musharraf of Pakistan maintains:

The decision was fairly easy. Technically it’s government job to frame counter-terrorism policy...My case was different as I wore multiple hats at that time. That is, being Army Chief, President and Chief Executive, I had influence over bureaucracy both military and civil, political arenas, academic and intellectual community, civil society...all segments that I briefed and consulted on the decision. The decision was in the best interest of the country. Dulgan(2009)

The key inference here is, Islamabad’s U-turn versus Taliban regime in Kabul was not an institutional and consensual based decision, rather it was essentially apersonal and individual decision of a military General in command. Ambassador Shamshad Ahmad’s following observation echoes the same point of view:

No matter how necessary or justified the policy turnaround was, it only showed the ad hoc and arbitrary nature of the decision-making process in Pakistan on national security and foreign policy issues during the days following 9/11. This was also reminiscent of many earlier policy decisions, including the one of inventing and then recognizing and supporting the Taliban regime. Duran (2008)

To quote one of the key ex-military aides of Musharraf:

The decision was taken earlier and then corps commanders, National Security Council members, and hand-picked political advisers were consulted...In doing so, General Musharraf missed the complexity of the issues involved...He should have drawn the line or limits of support to the United States. Wodak (2009)

So, what were the United States demands that General Musharraf readily agreed to? The US gave Pakistan a list of the following non-negotiable demands:

1. Stop Al-Qaeda operatives coming from Afghanistan to Pakistan, intercept arms shipments through Pakistan, and end all logistical support for Osama bin Laden;
2. Give blanket over-flight and landing rights to U.S. aircraft;
3. Give the US access to Pakistani naval and air bases and to the border areas between Pakistan and Afghanistan;
4. Turn over all intelligence and immigration information;
5. Condemn the September 11 attacks and curb all domestic expressions of support for terrorism;
6. Cut off all shipments of fuel to the Taliban, and stop Pakistani volunteers from going into Afghanistan to join the Taliban;
7. Note that, should the evidence strongly implicate Osama bin Laden and the Al Qaeda network in Afghanistan, and should the Taliban continue to harbour him and his accomplices, Pakistan will break diplomatic relations

with the Taliban regime, end support for the Taliban, and assist the U.S. in the aforementioned ways to destroy Osama and his network.

Was Islamabad's assurance of unstinted cooperation to Washington a tactical manoeuvre or a qualitative shift in its earlier Afghanistan (pro-Taliban) policy? General Pervez Musharraf in a public address to the nation on 19 September, 2001 proffered five reasons for choosing to offer unstinted co-operation to the US in its war against terrorism.

The five reasons for choosing this course of action were:

1. Secure Pakistan's strategic assets,
2. Safeguard the cause of Kashmir,
3. Prevent Pakistan from being declared a terrorist state,
4. Prevent an anti-Pakistani government from coming to power in Kabul,
5. Have Pakistan re-emerge politically as a responsible and dignified Nation.

The decision marked a U-turn in Pakistan's decades' long security policy with respect to Afghanistan and set in motion the redefinition of its strategic priorities accompanied by the immense challenges on the home front. Terming the decision as matter of national survival, President Musharraf in his nation-wide televised address on 19 September, 2001, said "at this juncture I am worried about Pakistan only...I give top priority to the defence of Pakistan. Defence of any other country comes later." This clearly signalled Afghanistan under Taliban as more of a strategic liability than an asset for Pakistan in the post-9/11 strategic milieu. It's a documented fact that Islamabad prior to 9/11 faced international pressure to seek the Taliban's compliance with international demands. Specifically, the closure of militants training camps and the handing over of Osama Bin Laden.

An eminent security analyst Syed Rifaat Hussain contends, the qualitative shift in Pakistan's pro-Taliban policy was based on several key considerations:

Come out on the right side of history; avoid American retribution; prevent the emergence of an Indo-US axis against Pakistan with dire consequences for country's survival; clear sense of gains: get sanctions lifted, put Pak-US ties back on track, gain international legitimacy for his military regime and most importantly create political and social space for Pakistan to deal with the blow-back effects' of the Taliban controlled Afghanistan on Pakistani society.

A critical point to be noted here is that though Islamabad abandoned its earlier pro-Taliban posture, it didn't amount to de-recognizing India as a major security threat in its national security perspective. In fact, the Indian threat was quoted as one of the key reasons to justify Islamabad's pro-US role in the war in Afghanistan. The unofficial reports of Indian offers to the United States, allowing the use of its military bases at Avantipur in India-controlled Kashmir, Adampur in the northwest state of Punjab and Jamnagar in Gujarat bordering Pakistan, critically informed Islamabad's reading of its geo-strategic environment. That is, no real shift occurred in the strategic mind box of the Musharraf government and Islamabad's threat perception with regard to Indian role in the region became more expansive. According to General Musharraf's key security aide:

Indian offer was motivated by a desire to ensure that Pakistan does not gain through an Indian default...Staging ground troops in India could pose a challenge, however, because India and Afghanistan do not share a border. Any troops based in India likely would have to be transported by air over Pakistan

Thus, General Musharraf's pro-US tilt in Afghanistan can be termed as a tactical move to end Pakistan's pre-9/11 problems relating to a faltering economy, diplomatic isolation and reining in the tide of political violence in the country, in addition to denying India strategic leverage and dominant role in the US led military campaign in Afghanistan. The decision was sold to public as a strategic necessity driven by the need to reclaim Pakistan as a moderate Muslim state and safeguard its national integrity. This narrative strengthened Musharraf's military rule and fitted well with his declarations of reforms prior to 9/11.

Following Pakistan's decision to join the international coalition against terrorism, Pakistan was successful in altering its earlier most sanctioned status and internationally isolated, economically fragile image. Pak-US relations once again registered a high point. On the sanctions front, U.S. President Bush in two separate orders on 22 September, 2001, and on 27 October, 2001 respectively, removed nuclear test related economic sanctions, democracy related sanctions on Pakistan and debt rescheduling through 2003. This removal of sanctions allowed Islamabad to receive \$600 million in Economic Support Funds (ESF) from the US. In 2002, Pakistan received an estimated \$624.5 million in development assistance and ESF.

General Musharraf decision to join the US camp set in motion a challenging phase of rethinking and recasting the national strategy on nuclear safety and security, Kashmir, and Afghanistan. Each of the stated policy objectives entailed a complex process of redefinition that had implications at the national, bi-lateral, regional and international levels.

Our War or not

In paragraph 6 of the speech, “The war against terrorism must be fought comprehensively, with vision and understanding. It should not erode the moral values of our society”. President General Pervez Musharraf make it clear that the war on terror is our war and it must be fought comprehensively with clear understanding of goals and consequences.

The section of society who believes on ideology of Zia is still not convinced that “War on Terror” is our war. Frighteningly the people with this thinking are in majority which not only shows the failure of government but also our society’s lack of understanding with geo-strategic circumstances. Mostly the religious political parties, number of religious scholars and masses from underdeveloped urban areas and rural areas are the believers of this ideology. Jamat-i-Islami and JUI which enjoyed very close ties with Zia is the major supporter of this school of thought. Interestingly not only the religious minded individuals are not the only supporter of this idea but also number of intellectuals and academics are in favour of it. Major example of people of this mindset is Maulana Abdul Aziz of Lal Masjid who refused to condemn Taliban and their massacre attack on Army Public School of Peshawar which caused a strong stir in society but somehow the influenced Maulana has not been under arrest and kept on delivering his hate speeches from Lal Masjid in capital of the country.

Action against Terrorism

In paragraph 5 of the speech, “Our intentions must be in no doubt. Our actions speak louder than words. We are acting against Al-Qaeda and its associates effectively. We have also acted against other organizations or groups involved in any form of terrorism”, President General Pervez Musharraf make it clear that we are acting against all kind of terrorism. By all accounts the record of Pakistan’s military, intelligence and security officials in capturing, killing and busting the Al-Qaeda elements remain successful. President Pervez Musharraf claimed in his memoir *In the Line of Fire*:

We have captured 689 and handed over 369 to the United States. We have earned bounties totalling millions of dollars. Those who habitually accuse us of not doing enough should simply ask the CIA how much prize money it has paid to the government of Pakistan.

Likewise, Major General Shaukat Sultan Khan, spokesman for Musharraf argues;

Pakistan has provided consistent support to the United States, assigning 70,000 Pakistani troops to the border region and assisting in the capture or killing of 700 members of Al Qaeda...The purpose behind moving security forces into the tribal area was to secure the western borders, to check the movement of people moving into Pakistan, to ensure that coalition operations in Afghanistan did not spill over into Pakistani territory, to nab the terrorists and to assist in development works in the FATA. PU (2007)

What is critical to note, there existed (and continue to do so) a nexus between Al-Qaeda and number of indigenous sectarian, ethnic, political, jihadi groups in Pakistan. According to the law enforcement agencies as well independent media accounts, Al-Qaeda’s operational, logistics and recruitment networks encompass, Jandollah, Harkatul Mujahedeen al Alami, Lashkar-e-Jhangvi, Al-Badar, Lashkar-e-Omar, Hartkatul-Islami, HUII, Jaish-e-Mohammad (JM), Jamiat al-Ansar and Sipah-e-Sahaba, in Pakistan. These linkages go back to the period of Afghan Jihad followed by civil war and Taliban rule in Afghanistan. Reportedly, Fazl-ur-Rehman Khalil, the leader of Harkat-ul-Mujahedin (Movement of Mujahedin), co-signed the 1999 edict by Osama bin Laden which called it a duty of every Muslim to kill Americans and Jews. Jamaat-al-Dawa acquired its 77-hectare Muridke estate with the help of a donation from Abdul Rehman Sherahi, who was arrested because of connections with al-Qaeda.

The very arrests of high profile Al-Qaeda leaders from 2002 onwards testify to the reach of Al-Qaeda in the mainland plus FATA, NWFP (now Khyber Pakhtunkhwa) and Baluchistan areas of Pakistan. For instance, Abu Zubaida (2002) was captured from a Lashkar-e-Taiba safe house in Faisalabad. Abu Omer and Abu Hamza (January 2003) were arrested from Sabiha Sharif’s (a member of the Jamaat-Islami) residence in Karachi. The number three in the Al-Qaeda hierarchy, Khalid Sheikh Mohammad along with Mustafa Hawsawi was arrested at the home of Abdul Qudoos, a Jamaat-Islami supporter, in March 2003. Similarly, Waleed Muhammad bin Attash, a suspect in the October 2000 attack on the USS Cole, is reported to have claimed the recruitment of a dozen Lashkar-e-Taiba workers for suicide missions against US targets.

Likewise, Musaad Aruchi, a nephew of Khalid Sheikh Mohammed with a \$1 million bounty on his head, was arrested in Karachi in June 2004. Tanzanian Ahmed Khalfan Ghailani was arrested in the city of Gujarat in July 2004. Pakistani intelligence agencies and security forces arrested Abu Faraj al-Liby, mastermind of two failed attempts on President Pervez Musharraf’s life, in Mardan (May 2005). Abu Hamza Rabia, an Al-Qaeda commander ranked the third most senior leader in the network, was killed in a tribal region of Pakistan bordering Afghanistan in December 2005. Mushin Musa Matwalli Atwah (also known as Abdul Rehman), an Egyptian Al-Qaeda member wanted for involvement in the 1998 bombing of the U.S. embassy in Kenya, was killed by Pakistani forces close to the Afghan border in April 2006.

According to the study published by Pakistan Institute of Peace Studies, from January 2002 to May 2006, more than 1,000 Al-Qaeda suspects had been arrested in Pakistan. The number of Al-Qaeda activists, killed in operations is above 1,000 in Pakistan. However, Pakistani media reported only 660 Al-Qaeda arrests. The nationality of the Al-Qaeda activists arrested is as follows:

70 from Algeria, 86 from Saudi Arabia, 20 from Morocco, 22 from United Arab Emirates, 11 from Libya, 7 from Kuwait, 20 from Egypt, 28 from Indonesia, 18 from Malaysia and 36 from the Western Asian Countries. Al-Qaeda arrests also included western nationals: 5 from USA, 2 from Australia and 11 from Great Britain.

In March 2002, Pakistan deployed nearly 100,000 troops around Tora Bora to block fleeing Al-Qaeda fighters from crossing over into Pakistan territory. According to official Pakistan figures, as of early 2003 more than 443 Al-Qaeda suspects belonging to 18 different nationalities have been handed over to the US authorities. Why Musharraf government handed over Al-Qaeda fighters plus Pakistani militants to US and not to their respective countries of origin remains a matter of debate within and beyond Pakistan. A senior intelligence official on condition of anonymity claims:

It is a big misperception that we picked people (including Pakistani nationals) and handed them to USA without approaching their country of origin. We had people from 39 countries and we called their Ambassadors but most of them refused to take them back...We could not have interrogated and lodged them all as we lacked interpreters and infrastructure to house them. Most of the governments that we approached asked us to handover their nationals specifically _hard core Al-Qaeda operatives to the United States

In addition to the Al-Qaeda arrests, Pakistan government banned and froze the bank accounts of the Al-Qaeda affiliated welfare organizations, such as Al-Rasheed Trust, Al-Rabeta Trust, and Al-Akhtar Trust – these decisions were later challenged in the provincial High Courts by the supporters of these organizations. Pakistan government in its report to the United Nations mandated Al-Qaeda Counter Terrorism Committee maintained:

Pursuant to UNSC resolutions 1267, 1333 and 1373, Pakistan has frozen the assets and accounts of a number of entities found involved in terrorist activities. The State Bank has issued directives and advisories toward this end.

Concept of “Enlightened Moderation”

After taking a wholly new stance in foreign policy, Musharraf started to implement his ideals internally. He introduced his vision of “Enlightened Moderation”. This vision includes the promotion of liberal values, new education system, promotion of soft image of Pakistan at global level, Women rights and right share in government and advancement of technology and Electronic Media in the state.

In 2000, Musharraf took his first major step according his liberal ideology. He tried to alter the Blasphemy Law, established under Zia’s “Islamization” in 1981. His second step was taking steps against militant, sectarianism and extremist organizations with in Pakistan. On January 12, 2002, Musharraf gave a speech against militant entities and condemned all unlawful extremist activities in Pakistan. He banned the foreign funding to the Madrassahs and asked them to teach modern and science related subjects. These first efforts although failed more or less but it proved to be start of new “Liberal Wave” in Pakistan.

Another major step taken by Musharraf was about the role and status of women in society. He was a profound advocate of Women rights and equality mostly based on Western ideology of Feminism. In 2002, during the election reforms, he fixed sixty reserve seats for women in General Assembly. Along with that women were also allowed to contest on general seats during elections. After 2002 elections seventy-two women became members of national assembly among whom twelve won on open elected seats.

Vital steps were taken by Musharraf to liberalize the society were the revolution of Electronic Media in Pakistan and modernizing education sector. Before 2000, Electronic media was relatively weak and almost non-existent in the country and revolved around one TV channel which was a government’s Media representation. Being a liberal person, Musharraf started to develop electronic media channels in Pakistan. For this purpose Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority (PEMRA) was established in 2002. This body started to issue license for establishing new Media Channels which became the base of electronic media revolution in Pakistan. Meanwhile educational reforms were introduced according to modern needs and fulfilling around modern technology especially in Information technology sector.

These Musharraf’s liberal and progressive policies started a new trend and produced new “Wave of Modernization” in Pakistan. A new Liberal class emerged with the country. The “Islamization” of General ZiaUIHaq diminished a bit especially after electronic media revolution.

As mentioned earlier one of the relational gap in our society is in education system of Pakistan. On one hand there are students of approximately 14,000 Madrassahs. This lot of students has their own social circle, specific educational mindset and being brought up in specific and confined environment. These students have the “Zia Mindset” on numerous issues specifically regarding war on terror. Taliban are still Mujahedeen, War

on Terror is War of US and our government and Army is fighting a wrong war on behalf of Western powers. The statement of Munawar Hassan, former head of Jamat-e-Islami in which he said that TTP militants are Shaheed while Pakistani Army Personnel are not Shaheed in this war on terror. Now this sentiment is accepted by a large section of our society.

The other section of our society which belongs to Elite Class, Students of Private English institutions and liberal academics hold the “Musharraf Ideology”. This section of our society strongly believes on policies of Musharraf, supporters of killing and executing of TTP militants and largely supports drone attacks with in Pakistani territory. The stance of this society was seen during Maulana Abdul Aziz issue, when a large number of Civil Society members protested outside Lal Masjid and demands for arrest of Maulana. This section is largely active on social media and on number of occasions blames Islam and religious scholars for almost every social issue. The hostility and gulf between both these sections is clear and yet again alarming not for themselves but for Pakistan.

In paragraph 12 of the speech, “I believe the way forward to adopt a two-pronged strategy a double pincer to build harmony, promote moderation, oppose extremism, and ensure justice. I called this strategy “Enlightened Moderation”. In paragraph 13 of the speech, “On one hand Muslim nations must assume their responsibility for internal reform and renewal. They are at the cross roads. They must eschew extremism and confrontation.” Again in paragraph 14 of the speech, “The international community specially advanced countries of the West, must deliver the other pincer of the strategy of “Enlightened Moderation”. They can do so:

- By helping the political disputes and situations where Muslim are being suppressed, such in Palestine and Kashmir;
- By rejecting attempts to equate terrorism with Islam; and
- By assisting the Muslim World in poverty alleviation and socio-economic development.”

Musharraf’s enlightened moderation narrative consisted of two prongs. First one concerned the Muslim world to break from the path of militancy, extremism and focus on socio-economic. The second one focused on the Western world specifically the United States to just role in the resolution of lingering Islamic world issues like Palestine and Kashmir, and also contribute towards the underdeveloped Muslim states. Plus this concept stressed unity among all member states of the United Nations in reclaiming true Islamic image as an ultimate way towards emancipation. President General Pervez Musharraf further clears that United Nations has a crucial role to play in the conception and execution of the strategy of “Enlightened Moderation”.

This concept of “Enlightenment through moderation” was well received by the Muslim leaders and added to Musharraf’s international image building campaign. His former spokesperson, Lt.General (retd) Rashid Qureshi in conversation with the author said:

General Musharraf was a visionary leader. He was conscious of dilemmas facing us and the Muslim world. He came to the conclusion that issues such as Kashmir cannot be resolved through force. So, best way is to adopt a pragmatic, moderate and enlightened worldview and policy.

However, on home front to bolster the concept of enlightened moderation the tradition of Sufism in Islam was exploited and several programmes were started to publicise Sufism. The aim of these programmes was to counter the extremism of the religious clerics who use the mosques to spread ill-will against the West and invite people for militant jihad. The idea was to highlight “divine love, peace and tolerance” that is the core of Sufi teachings as the alternative to “militant ideology”. The National Sufi Council was launched by President Musharraf at a grand ceremony in the historical city of Lahore on the occasion of Iqbal’s birthday on 9 November 2006. In the same month, an International Sufi conference was organized by the Punjab Institute of Languages, Art and Culture (PILAC) under the direction of the Chief Minister of the province, Chaudhry Pervaiz Elahi. The Sufi ideology of love and peace was promoted to combat the exclusivist slogans of the mullahs.

However, these actions were not well received by the majority of the Sufi and political community. Imran Khan, former cricketer turned politician, called these steps as: “sound-bites by military ruler to appease the Americans. Military rule under Musharraf nullifies the spirit of democracy that is essence of Enlightened Moderation in reality.”

Cause of Kashmir

In paragraph 19 of the speech, “Jammu and Kashmir has been rightly described as the most dangerous dispute in the world. A just solution of this dispute holds the key to peace and security in South Asia.” President General Pervez Musharraf make it clear that Jammu and Kashmir is the most blurring dispute in the world and if it is not solved peacefully, at the result there will be no peace, harmony and security in South Asia. Indian government are using force and coercive diplomacy to suppress the legitimate and basic right of Kashmiri people to exercise their right to self determination in accordance with the UN Security Council resolutions.

India also refuses Pakistan's offer of dialogue to resolve the Kashmir dispute. India always talks about cross-border terrorism to refuse the offer of dialogue. We all know that Kashmiri struggle for independence is indigenous. India seeks to exploit the international anti-terrorist sentiment after 9/11, to show the world that Kashmiri freedom struggle is delegitimize. On the contrary it is India which violates international law by refusing to implement UN Security Council resolutions and perpetrating gross and consistent violations of human rights in Kashmir. In the speech President General Pervez Musharaf invite India for dialogue on the issue of Kashmir and show the desire that with good will, we can find a just solution which is acceptable to India, to Pakistan and, above all, to the Kashmiri people.

Apart from addressing Kashmir, President General Pervez Musharaf claims in the speech that sustainable security in South Asia requires India and Pakistan to institute measures to ensure mutual nuclear restraint and a conventional arms balance. Unfortunately, India is embarked on a massive build-up of its conventional and nonconventional military capabilities – advanced offensive aircraft, ballistic and cruise missiles, ABM systems, nuclear submarines and an aircraft carrier. This will destabilize South Asia and erode strategic deterrence. Those powers which desire peace, stability and security in South Asia and oppose the proliferation of Weapons of Mass Destruction must review their decisions to offer such major strategic weapons systems to India. They must contribute to maintaining arms restraint and a military balance in South Asia.

Analysis of Islamic reference

In paragraph 11 Of the speech, “Islam is a faith of peace, harmony, and Justice. Islam is democracy in action.” President General Pervez Musharaf makes it clear that Islam is the religion of peace, harmony and justice. It upholds human rights, social equality, non-discrimination, freedom of speech. The protection of minorities is an article of faith in Islam. It does not discriminate on the basis of color, caste, creed or religion. Our Faith is dynamic, promoting constant renewal and adaptation, through the process of Ijtihad (or interpretation through consultations), Islam's vision is not trapped in any one period of history; it is modern and futuristic. Islam must not be confused with the narrow vision of a few extremists. Our religion Islam also gives us the lesson of Humanity and guides us towards the right path of completely success at each and every step. And in this way every next step is better than the previous step.

The most disquieting situation developing in our society especially in young generation is the fear from Islamic outlook and symbols. The responsible for developing this fear is by and large our local and international media. Every terrorist attack carried by Militants is shown exclusively on media. In this media reports the terrorists or a militant is usually a Muslim and carries the outlook with beard, head scalp and traditional clothes of Muslims. Now this image has been run and re-run on Media Channels for Million times. The effect of this media coverage and propaganda has affected the youngsters for whom a man with beard and head-scalp is a terrorist. The propaganda on electronic media is responsible of this mindset and Pakistani government need to take necessary measures for this very critical issue. Measures on emergency footings are needed to be taken because Pakistan is a Muslim country and large sections of masses carries this outlook. This issue will cause a further destabilization in our society and our already confused masses will further worsen this situation.

Hope for healthy and prosperous future

At the end of the speech President General Pervez Musharaf is hopeful for healthy and prosperous future of the World. The future of the world will be prosperous and healthy if everyone among us fulfils his responsibility with sincerity. He claims that we are on the cusp of a new Millennium. It is a decisive moment in history. We must decide whether to flow with the currents that threaten confrontation and the collapse of our civilization, or muster the collective will to chart the course of history towards a peaceful and cooperative global society. The leaders assembled here bear an enormous responsibility: to rescue our world from war and violence, poverty and pestilence; to redress inequity and impoverishment which breeds despair and destruction; to collectively construct a new global architecture of peace and prosperity for all peoples and nations. This speech contains more than one thousand and seven hundred words, and also leads to multi dimensions for analysis, but we sum up here that analysis a text on different level, we need quality not quantity.

Conclusion

This paper has analysed in the light of Fairclough notion of ideology, “meaning are produced through interpretations” Fairclough (1992). And in this regard we have range to clarify and identify the frame work of President General Pervez Musharaf's speech on Linguistics, and Political, ideological, critical and Islamic level. Following are our conclusions:-

The findings of the speech analysis have shown that using a different style in a different way using critical devices in his speech, President General Pervez Musharaf make his speech more fruitful, interesting and beneficial for development of his country as well as development for all.

To support the war on terror and acting against terrorism comprehensively shows that we took a strategic decision, based on the principles of humanity and our national interest. In action against terrorism our action speaks louder than words because we have arrested and killed more than 700 Al-Qaeda members.

Uses the concept of Enlightened Moderation in international forum promote the positive and soft image of Pakistan in front of the world

Uses of Islamic references in the speech like “Islam is a religion of peace”, shows that we are the wellwishers of “Human being”.

The overall underlying theme of the speech is “peace, security, Human Rights, development, equality, good governance etc” for the development of entire world including Pakistan. Without any doubt it is clear that we are the largest contributor to UN peacekeeping since 1960.

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